

IDENTIFYING THE IMPACT OF SMARTPHONE ADDICTION IN RELATION TO ACADEMIC ANXIETY, ACADEMIC PROCRASTINATION AND LIFE SATISFACTION OF SRI LANKAN UNIVERSITY STUDENTS

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Introduction

Smartphones are becoming an essential part of human lives within all ages around the world. People feel inseparable from their smartphones. (Lepp et al., 2015)

Smartphones can keep people connected anywhere at any time with the availability of internet. Specially among the younger generation, Smartphones are very famous. When it comes to universities in Sri Lanka, almost all the students have a smartphone.

There are many research that have been done to explore the relationships between smartphone addiction and possible correlations that are relevant to students' life, such as anxiety, academic procrastination and life satisfaction (Huang et al., 2013; Iskender & Akin, 2011; Lepp, 2014). However, it is hard to find similar kind of researches that have been performed in Sri Lankan context. Due to lack of studies in this research area and as a country of increasing considerable amount of smartphone ownership throughout the recent years, it is important to conduct a research regarding this topic in Sri Lankan context.

Research Objectives

- Identify the relationship between smartphone addiction and academic anxiety.

- Identify the relationship between smartphone addiction and academic procrastination.
- Identify the relationship between smartphone addiction and life satisfaction.

Literature Review

There are many scholars who have named problematic mobile phone or internet use as an addiction using terms such as ‘mobile phone addiction’, ‘smartphone addiction’ and ‘internet addiction’ (Mark, 2000), (Hong et al., 2012) after (Mark, 1995) has published his research study on the technological addictions.

The anxiety is associated with the increasing level of smartphone use including dependence and smartphone addiction (Hong et al., 2012; Iskender & Akin, 2011). That has been found out by many empirical studies.

Out of the studies that were conducted among university students regarding to this topic, a very few has focused specifically on the academic-related anxiety.

Academic procrastination is a common incident and it has been found that students often procrastinate when it comes to academic related activities (Klassen, 2009; Silverman & Lay, 1996). It is hard to find researches which were performed to find the relationship between academic procrastination and smartphone addiction particularly in Sri Lankan context.

There were several studies performed to investigate the relationship between the smartphone addiction and the life satisfaction and gained mixed findings (Yang, Asbury & Griffiths, 2018).

Based upon the above mentioned theoretical and empirical literature, there are several questions that need to be investigated empirically, specifically on the context of Sri Lankan Universities.

Methodology

This study has used a quantitative approach to conduct the research. It has proposed three hypotheses, according to the conceptual model that was used. To collect data, this study has used a survey based on an online questionnaire and it is distributed via online platforms among the University students.

Figure 2. Conceptual Model

Source: Yang, Asbury & Griffiths, 2018

Participants

This study's entire population is University students and its sample frame is undergraduates in Sri Lanka. This study has managed to get 92 responses.

Methods of measurement

Smartphone addiction was measured using the smartphone addiction scale short version (Kwon et al., 2013).

Academic anxiety was measured using modified version of the anxiety subscale of the academic emotions questionnaire (Pekrun, Goetz & Perry, 2005).

Academic procrastination was measured using irrational procrastination scale (Steel, 2010).

Life satisfaction is assessed by using the satisfaction with life scale (Diener, et al., 1985).

Results and Discussion

Table 2. Hypotheses Acceptance

Hypotheses	Path Coefficient	P Value (95% confidence level)	Hypotheses result (95% Confidence level)
H1: Smartphone Addiction positively impacts on Academic Anxiety	0.746	0.000	Accepted
H2: Smartphone Addiction positively impacts on Academic Procrastination	0.626	0.000	Accepted
H3: Smartphone Addiction Negatively impacts on Life Satisfaction	-0.066	0.639	Rejected

Findings

- Smartphone addiction has significant relationship with Academic Anxiety 0.746 (p 0.000).
- Smartphone addiction has significant relationship with Academic Procrastination 0.626 (p 0.000).
- Smartphone addiction has no significant relationship with Life Satisfaction -0.066 (p 0.639).

Discussion

In previous studies it is said that anxiety is associated with increasing smartphone addiction (Hong et al., 2012; Iskender & Akin, 2011). However, most of the previous studies were not focused specifically on the academic anxiety. According to Yang, Asbury and Griffiths (2018) it is said that problematic smartphone use has positively impacted on the academic anxiety. Similarly, present studies' findings also represent the same results.

When it comes to the procrastination, Yang, Asbury and Griffiths (2018) have found that the smartphone addiction positively and significantly impacts on academic procrastination. Present study also finds that smartphone addiction has positively and significantly impacted on the academic procrastination.

There are many studies which were performed to investigate the relationship between life satisfaction and smartphone addiction and gained different results in different studies. Hypotheses 3 in the present study has been rejected because smartphone addiction did not impact significantly on the life satisfaction.

Conclusion

Ultimately present study has found out that smartphone addiction has significantly impacted on academic anxiety and academic procrastination while there is no significant relationship between smartphone addiction and life satisfaction in Sri Lankan University students.

Theoretical/practical implications

From the findings, it can be said that students were not able to control the use of smartphones. To overcome this situation, more training and guidance may be useful in regulating smartphone use, how to benefit from smartphone, time management skills and providing skills.

Future Research

It can use new methods for exploring about the smartphone addiction since there are some applications to time track in the mobile phones.

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